

Societal Impact Highlights

Researcher: Catarina Roseta-Palma

Research Group: Economics

Case study: **Green Tax Reforms**

Summary

Most taxes have distortionary impacts, creating deadweight losses in several markets. However, taxes are necessary in most economies to support public spending, leaving policy-makers with a conundrum. Environmental taxes are an exception to the rule, since their aim is to correct pre-existing externalities; thus replacing other taxes with environmental taxes could maintain overall tax revenues while improving environmental and economic outcomes, a possibility known as the “double dividend”. Catarina Roseta-Palma has developed work on environmental and resource costs in several markets, such as water and energy, and in 2014 participated in the Portuguese Commission for Green Tax Reform, promoting a wide-ranging review of environmental taxes in the country.

Underpinning research

The review undertaken by the Commission covered various fields, including those of energy and water, which will be described separately. Roseta-Palma (2003) highlights the potential role of water taxes, combined with taxes on polluting inputs, while Monteiro and Roseta-Palma (2011) discuss residential consumer reactions to price increases. The latter article was one of the outcomes of research project “Tarifaqua” POCI/EGE/61306/2004 and fed into another research project on water prices, “Pricing and Behavioural Responses in the Water Sector”, PTDC/EGE-ECO/114477/2009, both coordinated by Roseta-Palma. She had already been involved in the definition of the economic regime of water charges in 2004-2005. The final outcome of this work was Portuguese DL 97/2008, which has now been revised by the Green Tax Reform Commission

to update and simplify water-charge application, as well as reduce some of the exemptions and benefits that had been previously granted.

As far as energy, its importance to economic growth is widely recognized and macroeconomic models without environmental effects are seen as incomplete. Roseta-Palma, Ferreira Lopes and Sequeira (2010) and Ferreira Lopes, Sequeira and Roseta-Palma (2013) study the link between economic growth and environmental outcomes. These articles were part of the outcome of project "Externalities, Equilibriums and Policy Lessons from Multi-Sector Models of Endogenous Growth", PTDC/EGE-ECO/102238/2008, where Roseta-Palma was a researcher. On the other hand, Robaina-Alves, Rodríguez and Roseta-Palma (2011) focus on the European Union Emissions Trading System. Understanding the latter, while not synonymous with environmental taxes due to its nature as a cap-and-trade system, is crucial to designing energy taxes, since most intensive energy use is done by firms covered by the EU ETS. Whether permits are given away, sold, or a mix of both, determines the distributive impacts on the various covered sectors, yet the inefficiency behind a scheme that only covers a part of carbon emissions, leaving other emitting sectors (such as transport) outside its remit, was clear.

Researchers: Catarina Roseta-Palma, Henrique Monteiro and Alexandra Ferreira Lopes have been researchers at BRU-IUL since 2008.

References to the research

- Ferreira-Lopes, A., T. Sequeira, C. Roseta-Palma (2013) "On the Effect of Technological Progress on Pollution: An Overlooked Distortion in Endogenous Growth", *Oxford Economic Papers*, 65, 394-416, doi:10.1093/oep/gps019
- Robaina Alves, M., M. Rodríguez, C. Roseta-Palma (2011) "Sectoral and regional impacts of the European Carbon Market in Portugal", *Energy Policy*, 39, 2528-2541, doi:10.1016/j.enpol.2011.02.018
- Monteiro, H., C. Roseta-Palma (2011), "Pricing for scarcity? An efficiency analysis of increasing block tariffs", *Water Resources Research*, 47, W06510, doi:10.1029/2010WR009200
- Roseta-Palma, C., A. Ferreira Lopes, T. Sequeira (2010) "Externalities in an Endogenous Growth Model with Social and Natural Capital", *Ecological Economics*, 69, 603-612, doi:10.1016/j.ecolecon.2009.09.008
- Roseta-Palma, C. (2003) "Joint Quantity/Quality Management of Groundwater", *Environmental and Resource Economics*, 26, 86-106, doi: 10.1023/A:1025681520509

Details of the impact

The Green Tax Reform was widely reported in the media, mainly due to the introduction of the new charge on lightweight plastic bags, however this reform included a number of other taxes and charges affecting fuels, vehicle registration, water and waste. The most important outcome of the above-mentioned work was the publication of the Portuguese Green Tax Reform on the 31st of December 2014 (Lei nº 82-D/2014), although many proposals were altered or dropped and the challenge of turning theoretical insights into legislation that could be accepted by decision makers was clear.

The new carbon tax on fuels was established as an additional term on already existing fuel taxes, for simplicity. After much discussion, the Commission settled on a flexible value with a link to the EU ETS carbon price given the goal of eventually achieving similar carbon prices for all sectors (Robaina-Alves et al, 2013). Although the tax is fairly low for 2015 (5€/ton was used as reference, yielding an increase of about €0,015 cents per liter in gas and diesel), the law states that the yearly values will be calculated based on the prices in EU ETS permit auctions. On transport, vehicle registration taxes (which already had a carbon component) climbed around 3%, with hybrids benefitting from lower taxes and electric vehicles excluded, as before. A few tax benefits were strengthened, a temporary end-of-life incentive scheme was re-instated, and some benefits for car-sharing and bike-sharing schemes were introduced.

Some relevant changes to the water and waste charges were approved. In particular, values were updated: for example, the landfill charge increases from 5,5 €/ton to 11€/ton in 2020, to tackle the fairly high proportion of landfilled waste we still have (54% in 2012), although it should be noted that the Commission's proposal was 20€/ton in 2020. A few exemptions and reductions were revoked, but this proved to be quite a difficult task: although the Commission attempted to bring water charges closer for different users with similar impacts, the final version maintains special reductions for utility wastewater discharges and IPPC installations, for example, while some hydropower dams will continue to benefit from guaranteed capacity payments even when droughts occur and they are unable to produce. A new charge on lightweight plastic bags was approved, of €0,08 plus VAT, which will stop retailers giving away plastic bags for free, a policy that has placed Portugal in the top of plastic bag consumption according to estimates from the European Commission (nearly 500 bags per capita per year). The outcomes of this policy should be quantifiable as soon as data for 2015 is published.

The expected net revenue from the new environmental taxes is around €160 million per year, most of which associated with the new carbon tax. On the one hand, the Commission was

criticized for not going far enough: for such small values the modelled impacts for 2020, 2030 and 2050 considering various revenue-recycling alternatives, although generally positive (lower emissions and public debt, long-term increase in employment and GDP), were rather modest. On the other, there were some very negative reactions from affected sectors (such as plastic, oil and transport companies), and the revenue recycling instrument is not clearly specified in the law. An ex-post assessment of the impact of the Reform must be undertaken, again when more data is available.

Other outcomes of the work were the participation in several conferences and workshops to disseminate research results. Among these, we can highlight:

- “Fiscalidade ambiental: porquê, como, para quê?”, Colóquio Fiscalidade Ambiental e Desenvolvimento Sustentável, 2014
- “Analysis of Water Prices in Urban Systems: Experience from Three Basins in Southern Portugal”, VIII Congresso Ibérico de Gestão e Planeamento da Água, Lisboa 2013
- “O valor da água”, Jornadas da Engenharia do Ambiente 2012, Instituto Superior Técnico, Lisboa, Fevereiro, 2012
- “Regulation of Water, Wastewater and Municipal Solid Waste in Portugal”, Fondazione per l'Ambiente, Turin, 2011
- “Análise Económica da Água: o que mudou em Portugal”, conferência “Política da Água”, Coimbra, 2011

Sources to corroborate the impact

- <http://www.pwc.pt/pt/pwcinforfisco/reforma/2015/pwc-reformas-2015.pdf>
- <http://app.parlamento.pt/webutils/docs/doc.pdf?path=6148523063446f764c3246795a5868774d546f334e7a67774c336470626d6c7561574e7059585270646d467a4c31684a535339305a58683062334d76634842734d6a55334c56684a5353356b62324d3d&fich=ppl257-XII.doc&Inline=true>
- <http://www.pbbr.pt/en/component/acymailing/archive/view/listid-1-mailinglist/mailid-57-final?tmpl=component>
- http://www.jornaldenegocios.pt/economia/impostos/irs/reforma_do_irs/detalhe/tax_a_sobre_sacos_de_plastico_avanca_fiscalidade_verde_da_150_milhoes_ao_irs.html
- <http://www.apambiente.pt/index.php?ref=17&subref=1104>
- http://www.crescimentoverde.gov.pt/wp-content/uploads/2014/10/ReformaFiscalidadeVerde_GreenTaxReform_emagazine.pdf